

Partial Purification and Physicochemical Properties of Arginase from the Liver of *Tilapia zilli*

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Abstract

The study of the catalytic and physicochemical characteristics of the *Tilapia Zilli* liver arginase was carried out to provide information describing the survival of this fish species in the gold-mine reservoir. *Tilapia zilli* liver arginase was isolated and partially purified with 80% ammonium sulphate precipitation and CM-Sephadex C-25 ion exchange chromatography. The enzyme was purified with a specific activity and yield of 51.721 U/mL and 12.35% respectively. The enzyme had Km and Vmax values of 25 mM and 6.77 U/mL, respectively. Enzyme activity was optimum at pH 6.0 and temperature of 80 °C. Fe²⁺ and Hg²⁺ were strong inhibitors of enzymes in the inhibitory experiments. The findings demonstrated that amino acids do not inhibit the enzyme. In summary, *Tilapia zilli*'s survival in the gold mine reserve is significantly influenced by the physiological functions of its liver arginase.

Keywords: Arginase, *Tilapia zilli*, Gold mine, Liver

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Introduction

Tilapia zilli, commonly known as the Zilli tilapia, is a freshwater fish species that has garnered significant attention in scientific research (Shinkafi *et al.*, 2023) due to its unique enzymatic abilities and relevance in various fields, particularly in aquaculture and biomedical studies (Farrag *et al.*, 2021). The enzymatic abilities of *Tilapia Zilli* are noteworthy, as they possess a variety of digestive enzymes that facilitate the breakdown of complex substances (Niyibizi, 2023). These digestive enzymes include proteases, lipases, and amylases, which play a crucial role in their ability to utilize diverse diets efficiently (Shinkafi *et al.*, 2023; Ismail *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, research has been aligned towards the investigation of *Tilapia zilli* enzymatic profiles (Bamidele *et al.*, 2012), thereby helping scientists to develop better diagnostic tools and

preventive measures to combat diseases in aquaculture. Thus, *Tilapia zilli* is valuable for understanding fish health and the impact of pathogens in aquaculture settings (Farrag *et al.*, 2021). Arginase is a manganese-dependent enzyme found in practically all organisms and is a significant component of *Tilapia zilli*'s enzymatic profile (Okonji, 2014). In the urea cycle, arginase is essential because it transforms L-arginine into ornithine and urea for the excretion of nitrogen (Li *et al.*, 2022; Caldwell *et al.*, 2018). Fish-derived enzymes, including arginase, may offer novel biochemical properties useful for biomedical and industrial applications (Khan *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, arginase has therapeutic applications in treating arginine-related disorders, such as hyperargininemia and cardiovascular diseases (Caldwell *et al.*, 2018). Based on previous research which has not reported on the isolation

and purification of arginase from *Tilapia zilli*; not to mention the investigation of its properties, this current research was focused on partially purifying arginase from the liver of *Tilapia zilli*. In addition, this research investigated the properties of *Tilapia zilli* liver arginase to reveal unique enzymatic characteristics, such as temperature stability, pH tolerance, and substrate specificity; as these parameters can be exploited in biotechnology, agriculture, and industrial processes.

Furthermore, this study considers *Tilapia zilli* as an important model organism for various research applications (Niyibizi, 2023); based on its rapid growth rate, adaptability to different environmental conditions, and ease of breeding (Ismail *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, its genetic makeup has been researched for insights into evolutionary biology, species adaptation, and population dynamics, contributing to conservation efforts and the management of fish stocks. The study of purified arginase from *Tilapia zilli* liver will provide insights into the metabolism of nitrogenous waste in fish, and help in comparing its structure, activity, and stability with that of other species, including mammals, amphibians, and other fish (Khan *et al.*, 2022). Also, studying arginase properties can aid in developing better fish feeds by optimizing protein utilization and reducing ammonia toxicity in fish farms (Caldwell *et al.*, 2018).

Additionally, the current area of study is an abandoned gold mine reservoir in Osun State's Atakunmosa West Local Government Area, which is situated in Igun village. With an altitude of 299 meters, it spans latitude 07°31'N-07°35'N and longitude 004°30'E-004°43'E. To accommodate Nigeria's mining needs, streams that supply the community, like Oika, Eleripon, and Osun, were impounded to create reservoirs (Atobatele, 2008; Komolafe and Arawomo, 2008). The rocky mountainous landscape of Igun hamlet is covered in dense undergrowth and towering trees with high canopies, making it part of a lush tropical rainforest zone. The area is prevalent in narrow valleys and steep hills which renders accessibility difficult. The inhabitants of the community are farmers. Cash and food crops such as cocoa, kolanut, oil palm, orange, timber, maize, banana, cassava and breadfruit are produced.

Materials and Methods

Materials

Reagents and chemicals utilized for the current research were of pure and analytical grade. Tris base, manganese chloride tetrahydrate, zinc chloride, sodium chloride, tris HCL, L-histidine, phosphoric acid, L-alanine, magnesium chloride, L-proline, L-tyrosine, L-tryptophan, L-cysteine, p-amino benzaldehyde, citric acid, monosodium dihydrogen phosphate, sodium citrate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate were obtained from Kermel Reagent Company Limited, Tianjin, China. Hydrochloric acid, ammonium sulphate (enzyme grade), potassium chloride, urea, tin chloride and sodium chloride were purchased from BDH Chemical Limited, Poole, England. Arginine, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), Coomassie Brilliant-Blue was obtained from Sigma Chemical Company, St. Louis, Mo., USA. CM-Sephadex C-25 was obtained from Pharmacia Fine Chemicals, Uppsala, Sweden. Other chemicals as well as solvents were procured from reputable chemical firms.

Sample collection

Tilapia fish (*Tilapia zilli*) was obtained from the Igun gold mine reservoir located at Igun-Ijesha, Osun state. The samples were recognized and verified at Obafemi Awolowo University's Zoology Department in Ile-Ife, Osun State.

Enzyme Extraction

The liver tissue from *Tilapia zilli* was excised from the fish and rinsed to remove blood stains and other dirt. About 10.92 g of *Tilapia zilli* liver was homogenously prepared in five (5) different volumes of 0.01 M Tris buffer (pH 7.2). After centrifugation, the debris was disposed-off and the supernatant was gathered. Protein concentration and arginase activity were measured in an aliquot of the supernatant.

Arginase Assay

The Kaysen and Strecker (1973) approach was used to measure arginase activity. The final concentration of the reaction mixture was 2.0 mM Tris-HCl buffer at pH 9.5 with 1.0 mM MnCl₂, 0.33 M arginine, and 100 µl of the enzyme. This resulted in a final volume of 0.50 ml. At 30°C, the mixture went through incubation for 10 minutes. 2.5 ml of Ehrlich reagent was added to stop the reaction. After 20 minutes, the absorbance was measured at 450 nm. A standard urea curve created by changing the urea concentration between 0.1 µmol and 1 µmol was used to measure the amount of urea produced. The quantity of

arginase that will generate one micromole of urea per minute at 37°C was recorded as its unit of activity.

Determination of Protein

Bradford's (1976) approach, which used bovine serum albumin (BSA) as a standard and interpolated protein absorbance from the BSA standard curve, was used to measure the protein content. There were 1000 µl of Bradford reagent and 200 µl of the enzyme in the reaction mixture. At 595 nm, the absorbance was measured.

Ammonium Sulphate Precipitation

After centrifugation, the supernatant was conditioned to 80% saturation with ammonium sulphate by stirring and occasionally adding solid ammonium sulphate for approximately an hour. The mixture was centrifuged for 30 minutes at 4000 rpm after being left for 18 hours. A 0.01 M solution of Tris buffer (pH 7.2) was dialysed against the ammonium sulphate precipitate on multiple occasions. Following centrifugation, the dialysate was collected, and the protein content and arginase activity of the supernatant were measured. After that, the resin was packed into a 1.5 × 10 cm column and allowed to equilibrate with 0.1 M Tris-HCl buffer at pH 7.2. To get rid of the unbound protein, the column was cleaned using 0.01 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.2). Then, 0.1 M NaCl was gradually eluted in the same buffer. At an hourly rate of 40 millilitres, fractions of 2 millilitres were extracted from the column. The protein content and arginase activity of the column fractions were measured.

Ion-Exchange Chromatography on CM-Sephadex C-25

Five grammes (5g) of the resin were boiled in distilled water for an hour in order to pretreat the CM Sephadex C-25 cation exchanger. After 30 minutes, 100 ml of 0.1 M HCl was added. The acid was then decanted, and the resin was repeatedly cleaned with distilled water to guarantee that the acid was completely removed. The resin was then thoroughly raised with distilled water to eliminate any remaining residues of the base, and 100 ml of 0.1 M NaOH was added. The resin was then decanted after 30 minutes. After that, the resin was packed into a 1.5 × 10 cm column and allowed to equilibrate with 0.1 M Tris-HCl buffer at pH 7.2. To get rid of the unbound protein, the column was cleaned using 0.01 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.2). Then, 0.1 M NaCl was gradually eluted in

the same buffer. At an hourly rate of 40 millilitres, fractions of 2 millilitres were extracted from the column. The protein content and arginase activity of the column fractions were measured.

Determination of Kinetic Parameters

Varying the arginine concentrations between 25 mM and 225 mM allowed for the determination of the kinetic parameters (K_m and V_{max}). Lineweaver and Burk's (1934) double reciprocal plot was used to determine the kinetic parameters.

Effect of pH

At various pH values, the impact of pH on arginase activity was measured. Using buffers with varying pH values, "1 mM Tris buffer (pH 8.0), 0.01 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.0-7.0), 0.01 M citrate buffer (pH 3.0-5.0), and borate buffer (pH 9.0-10.0)", the pH values were adjusted. Each reaction mixture included 0.33 M of arginine, 0.05 ml of the enzyme, and 1 mM of the various buffers.

Effect of Temperature

Arginase activity was measured at a range of temperatures from 30 to 100 degrees Celsius. After 10 minutes of incubation at the chosen temperature, 50 µl of the enzyme that had already undergone incubation at the same temperature was added to the assay mixture to start the reaction.

Effect of Metals

Following the method ascribed to Kaysen and Strecker (1973), the impact of the divalent cations Na^+ , Hg^{2+} , and Fe^{3+} on arginase activity was measured. 50 µl of arginase, 25 µl of the metals, 1.0 mM Tris Buffer, pH 9.5, and 0.33 M arginine were in the reaction mixture. Ehrlich's reagent was added to end the reaction in the reaction mixture after incubation for ten minutes at room temperature.

Effect of Amino Acids

Using arginine as the substrate, the effects of various amino acids on arginase activity were examined. Amino acids used to monitor the effect of arginase were L-histidine, L-proline, L-alanine, L-cysteine, L-tryptophan, L-tyrosine. The reaction mixture was made up of 1.0 mM of the various amino acids, 1 mM $MnCl_2$, 1.0 mM Tris Buffer, and 50 µl of arginase from *Tilapia zilli*. There was incubation of the reaction mixture for 10 minutes; followed by its stoppage with the addition of Ehrlich's reagent.

Statistical analysis

Every experimental assay was carried out three times. Data was collated and analyzed as mean and standard deviation. GraphPad Prism and Microsoft Excel software were used to present the results obtained.

Results

Purification of Arginase

Table 1 provides a summary of the findings for the partial isolation of arginase from *Tillapia zilli*

liver. Likewise, Figure 1 displays the elution curve following ion exchange chromatography. The chromatographic technique gave a prominent peak (used for this research). Dialysis of the crude sample against 80% Ammonium Sulphate precipitation reduced the specific activity of arginase. In addition, CM Sephadex C-50 laden ion-exchange chromatography was used to purify arginase extracted from the liver of *Tilapia zilli*. Arginase from the liver of *Tilapia zilli* exhibited the 51.7211 U/mg protein as specific activity, 12.35% yield, and 0.1235 purification-fold.

Table 1: An overview of the process used to extract arginase from *Tilapia zilli* liver

Steps of Purification	Total Protein (mg)	Total Activity (U/mL)	Specific Activity (U/mg)	Purification Fold	Yield (%)
Crude Sample	0.2826	118.3835	418.9084	1.00	100
80% Ammonium Sulphate precipitation	0.1954	22.3290	114.2733	0.27	27.27
CM Sephadex C-50 "Ion-Exchange Chromatography"	0.0918	4.7480	51.7211	0.1235	12.35

Figure 1: Ion Exchange Chromatography of Arginase from the Liver of *Tillapia zilli*

Kinetic Parameters

Figure 2 shows the Lineweaver-Burk plot used to calculate the Km and Vmax of arginase from *Tillapia Zilli* liver. The plot highlighted in Figure 2 is the graphical representation of the Michaelis-Menten equation from this current study involving arginine concentrations ranging

from 25 mM to 225 mM. Figure 2 showed linear trends correlating the reciprocal of arginase activity with the reciprocal of arginine (substrate) concentration. It is observed that as the reciprocal of the concentration of arginine increased, the reciprocal of arginase activity also increased; thereby allowing for the

measurement of critical kinetic parameters namely V_{max} and K_m of an enzyme-catalyzed reaction.

Figure 2: Lineweaver-Burk plot of $1/V$ at varying concentrations of Arginine between 25 mM and 225 mM

Table 2 provides a summary of the K_m and V_{max} pertaining to arginine metabolism in the liver of *Tilapia zilli*. Both K_m and V_{max} are critical in understanding the efficiency of

arginase enzyme and its affinity for arginine as substrate. It was observed that the values of K_m and V_{max} of *Tilapia Zilli* liver arginase were 25 mM and 6.77 $\mu\text{mol/ml/min}$ respectively.

Table 2: Concise presentation of Kinetic Parameters from the *T. zilli* liver arginase using arginine as substrate

Substrate	K_m (mM)	V_{max} ($\mu\text{mol/ml/min}$)
Arginine	25	6.77

Effect of pH on Arginase from the liver of *Tilapia zilli*

It was discovered that the *Tilapia Zilli* liver's arginase activity peaked at pH 6.0 (Figure 3).

50 mM citrate buffer (pH 3.0-5.0), 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 6.0-7.0), and 50 mM borate buffer (pH 9.0-10.0) were used to find the ideal pH.

Figure 3: Effect of pH on *T. zilli* Liver Arginase Activity

Effect of Temperature on Arginase from the liver of *Tillapia zilli*

By testing the enzyme's activity at temperatures ranging from 30 to 100 degrees Celsius, the

impact of temperature on its activity was ascertained. The study examined the effect of temperature on the activity of arginase from *Tillapia zilli*'s liver and found that the enzyme functions best at 80°C (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Effect of Temperature on the Activity of *T. zilli* Liver Arginase

Effect of Some Divalent Metal Ion on arginase activity from liver of *Tillapia zilli*

The effects of metal ions (Na⁺, Fe³⁺, and Hg²⁺) at concentrations of 10 mM, 1.0 mM, and 0.1

mM were displayed in Table 3. As indicated by the proportion of residual activity at varying salt concentrations, the data in Table 3 illustrates how different metal ions affect the arginase activity of *T. zilli* liver.

Table 3: Effect of metal ions on the activity of *T. zilli* liver arginase

SALTS (mM)	% Residual Activity		
	0.1 mM	1.0 mM	10 mM
NaCl	56.05	53.52	53.52

FeCl₃	49.15	48.06	46.43
HgCl₂	51.88	43.15	66.61

Inhibitory effect of Amino Acids arginase activity from liver of *Tillapia zilli*

The inhibitory effect of alanine, cysteine, valine, proline, aspartic acid, serine, and glutamic acid

was investigated on the activity of arginase from the liver of *Tillapia zilli*. The result is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Percentage Activity of Various Amino Acids with Respect to Arginine

AMINO ACID	% ACTIVITY
Arginine	100.00
Tyrosine	90.48
Alanine	88.09
Proline	80.95
Tryptophan	71.43
Histidine	64.28
Cysteine	57.14

The data presented in Table 4 elucidates the percentage activity of various amino acids in relation to arginine (serving as the baseline with a defined activity level of 100%). It was observed that tyrosine, alanine, proline, tryptophan, histidine and cysteine exhibited substantial percentage activity of 90.48%, 88.09%, 80.95%, 71.43%, 64.28% and 57.14% respectively. This comparative analysis sheds light on the functional roles that different amino acids may play in biochemical processes, particularly in relation to their reactivity and potential contributions to metabolic pathways.

Discussion

Arginase from the liver of *Tilapia zilli* was purified using a procedure that included precipitation by ammonium sulphate and CM Sephadex-mediated ion-exchange chromatography. The results showed a specific activity of 51.7211 U/ml, with a percentage recovery of 0.1235. The specific activity of arginase obtained in this study (51.7211 U/mg protein) is greater than the range of values "5.21 to 40 U/mg protein" from different research (Okonji *et al.*, 2011; Al-Saad *et al.*, 2021). For grasshopper gut arginase, Okonji *et al.* (2013) documented a specific activity of 3.7 U/mg of protein, while Ehigie *et al.* (2010) reported a specific activity of 5.7 µmol/min per mg of protein for freshwater prawn hepatopancreas arginase. Dabir *et al.*, (2005) purified *Vigna catjang* cotyledon arginase by

using a procedure involving ion exchange chromatography as one of its purification steps. Kaysen and Strecker (1973) purified rat liver arginase through a procedure involving two heating steps, after which there was ion exchange chromatography on cationic exchangers. Okonji *et al.* (2013a) highlighted 3.7 µmol/min per mg protein as a specific activity for adult cockroach gut arginase. Okonji *et al.*, (2013b) also reported 6.18 µmol/min per mg protein as specific activity for *Heteroti snilocutis* arginase. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* arginase exhibited a specific activity of 655 units/mg (Green *et al.*, 1990).

Several values of Km have been highlighted for arginase enzymes from several sources. According to these reports, the Km values of uricotelic species range from 40 mM to 158 mM (Porembaska, 1973), whereas those of ureotelic organisms fall between 1 mM and 20 mM (Mora *et al.*, 1965b). According to this recent study, *Tillapia zilli*'s liver contains arginase with Km and Vmax of 25 mM and 6.77 µmol/ml/min, respectively. The Km value obtained compares very well with those of other sources though it falls within the range for those of ureotelic arginases. According to Okonji *et al.* (2010), *Z. variegates* (grasshopper) has a Km of 40 mM. The gills and foot muscles of a marine mollusc (*Chitonlatus*) have Km values of 25 mM and 30 mM, respectively, according to Carvajal *et al.* (1998). Km values of 40 mM for grasshopper gut arginase and 12.5 mM for freshwater prawn hepatopancreas arginase were reported by

Okonji *et al.* (2013) and Ehigie *et al.* (2010), respectively. Also, from hepatic cytosolic arginase, Srivastava & Ratha (2013) reported the K_m for arginase as 2.65 ± 0.39 mM, and V_{max} as 28.68 ± 1.23 μ mol urea/hour/milligram protein; suggesting a low affinity for arginine, coupled with a less significant enzymatic turnover rate. The impact of pH is one of the most studied variables affecting arginase activity. In the context of biochemical reactions, the pH of the environment can profoundly influence enzyme structure and, consequently, its catalytic efficiency. Enzymes are proteins that possess specific three-dimensional conformations, which are sensitive to changes in pH. In this study, the effect of pH on *Tilapia zilli* liver arginase gave an optimum pH of 6.0; suggesting that *T. zilli* liver arginase may partake in a critical metabolic role occurring in slightly acidic environments (Okonji *et al.*, 2011), potentially reflecting its ecological niche or the conditions prevalent in its native habitat (Tkaczenko *et al.*, 2024). However, finding on pH from this current study is different from some reported optimum pH for arginases from different sources. According to Okonji *et al.* (2010), grasshopper arginase prefers a pH of 8. According to Ehigie *et al.* (2010), the ideal pH for arginase from the giant freshwater prawn's hepatopancreas is 8.5. A basic optimal pH of 9.5-10.1 was reported for some mammalian arginases (Jenkinson *et al.*, 1996). According to McGee *et al.* (2004), *Helicobacter pylori* arginase and *Bacillus anthracis* have optimal pH values of 6.1 and 6.0, respectively. Thus, it is established that optimal pH values for arginase activity are often maintained within a similar range across diverse taxa; thereby presenting *T. zilli*'s biological role and evolutionary adaptations in various environments.

Numerous ideal temperatures have been found when the effects of temperature on arginase activity were examined. The investigation of temperature's influence on the activity of *T. zilli* liver arginase will elucidate the relationship between thermal dynamics and enzymatic function. In this work, the activity of *T. zilli* liver arginase was measured across a temperature range from 30°C to 100°C; after an optimum temperature of 80°C was obtained when Mn^{2+} was available. However, beyond the optimal temperature of 80°C, the structure of arginase began to destabilize; thereby resulting in the loss of catalytic efficiency and ultimately leading to a significant decrease in arginase activity. Thus, arginase from *T. zilli* will exhibit maximal activity at 80°C, after which there is a marked

decline as the temperature approaches 100°C. From previous studies, *S. monsoni* arginase has an optimal temperature of 37°C, according to Fitzpatrick *et al.* (2009); for wild-type arginase rat liver, Lavulo *et al.* (2001) reported an optimal temperature of 70°C. Similarly, Okonji *et al.* (2013) presented an optimum temperature of 40°C for grasshopper (*Zonocerus variegatus* Linn) gut arginase. Ehigie *et al.* (2010) identified an optimal temperature of 35°C for hepatopancreas arginase derived from giant freshwater prawns. Al-Saad *et al.* (2021) also presented an optimal temperature of 35°C for serum arginase of both type II-diabetes and healthy Iraqi patients.

Inhibition studies involving various amino acids were carried out on *T. zilli* arginase; however, arginine was the baseline. Arginine, being the reference point, is pivotal in numerous physiological functions, including protein synthesis, nitric oxide production, and modulation of various cellular processes (Li *et al.*, 2022; Caldwell *et al.*, 2018). From Table 4, tyrosine, alanine, proline, tryptophan, histidine and cysteine exhibited substantial activity of 90.48%, 88.09%, 80.95%, 71.43%, 64.28% and 57.14% respectively, none of them reached the full activity threshold established by arginine. Famakinwa *et al.* (2023) reported that L-serine, L-valine, L-glutamic acid, and L-aspartic acid showed moderate inhibition of 63%, 60%, 69.1% and 65.4% respectively on *Oryctes rhinoceros*' larva gut arginase. Additionally, L-lysine, L-proline, L-glutamic acid, L-aspartate, L-aspartic acid, L-valine and L-serine inhibited arginase activity from the liver of *Kinixy erosa* (tortoise) by less than 50%, according to Okonji *et al.* (2012). The amino acids valine, proline, aspartate, and lysine did not inhibit *Z. variegates* gut arginase, according to Okonji *et al.* (2013). According to Okonji (2014), L-proline and L-aspartate also mildly reduced the liver arginase of *Heterotis niloticus*. Agboola *et al.* (2021) found that whereas tryptophan, proline, histidine, tyrosine, and alanine had strong inhibitory effects on arginase activity, cysteine retained 81% of the activity of arginase extracted from the stomach of cane rats (*Thryonomys swinderianus*) when arginine was replaced with cysteine.

An important attribute peculiar to all arginases studied "whether eukaryotes or prokaryotes" is the influence of cations on their activity (Malik *et al.*, 2018). The activator of the enzyme is Mn^{2+} (Quiñones *et al.*, 2015); however, most importantly required divalent cations that influence arginase activities are Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{2+} ,

Co²⁺ and Cd²⁺ (Folashade *et al.*, 2019; Okonji *et al.*, 2014). It was observed from this current study that sodium chloride (NaCl) demonstrates a relatively stable effect on arginase activity, with residual activity percentages of 53.52%, 53.52%, and 56.05% at 10 mM, 1.0 mM, and 0.1 mM concentrations, respectively. This effect of NaCl on arginase indicates that it may have a minor inhibitory effect on arginase activity at higher concentrations. In contrast to NaCl, ferric chloride (FeCl₃) salt exhibited a more pronounced decline in arginase activity. At 0.1 mM, the residual activity dropped to 49.15%, further decreasing to 48.06% at 1.0 mM, and 46.43% at 10 mM. This trend suggests that Fe³⁺ ions may significantly interfere with the enzymatic function of arginase from *Tilapia zilli* liver, likely due to alterations in enzyme conformation or active site accessibility. Lastly, mercuric chloride (HgCl₂) presented an interesting pattern; showing a residual activity of 51.88% at 0.1 mM, which is relatively high compared to the other two metal ions. However, this value plummets to 43.15% at 1.0 mM, indicating a strong inhibitory effect of mercuric ions (Hg²⁺) at 1.0 mM concentration. Notably, the residual activity of HgCl₂ anomalously increased to 66.61% at 10 mM; possibly suggesting a potential compensatory mechanism or a complex interaction between the enzyme and Hg²⁺ ions at higher concentrations, warranting further investigation into the biochemical pathways involved. In a related study, in the liver arginase of *Ametermes eveuncifer*, Mn²⁺ satisfied the arginase metal ion requirement but arginase activity was inhibited by Zn²⁺ (Folashade *et al.*, 2019). Also, Folashade *et al.* (2019) discovered that arginase activity in *Ametermes eveuncifer* was strongly enhanced due to the availability of Mn²⁺ and Ni²⁺; but was slightly inhibited by the availability of K⁺, Ba²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Na⁺. Okonji *et al.* (2013) observed that arginase activity obtained from grasshopper (*Zonocerus variegatus* Linn) gut was activated by Na⁺, NH₄⁺ and Hg²⁺ indicated as NaCl, NH₄Cl and HgCl₂ salts respectively. Famakinwa *et al.* (2023) highlighted that purified arginase from the gut of *Oryctes rhinoceros* larvae was activated by CaCl₂, BaCl₂ and HgCl₂ at 1 mM. In conclusion, *Tilapia zilli*'s liver contains arginase with traits similar to arginases found in other sources. The fact that *Tilapia zilli*'s liver contains this enzyme raises the possibility that it contributes to the *T. zilli*'s energy production. Additionally, kinetic and physicochemical characteristics compared favourably to those of other ureotelic arginases,

establishing the critical role played by the enzyme in *Tilapia zilli*'s survival in the gold-mine reservoir. Further study is needed to examine the expression of the enzyme in all tissues of the fish.

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